

D7.3 CDUE-Plan, second update

Communication, Dissemination, Upscaling and Exploitation Plan of the Europe-LAND project

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List of Abbreviations and Acronyms

CDUE	Communication, dissemination, upscaling, exploitation
CoP	(online) Community of Practice
HAW (Hamburg)	University of Applied Sciences Hamburg
KPI	Key performance indicator
WP	Work package

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Executive Summary

This **second update of the** Communication, Dissemination, Upscaling and Exploitation (CDUE) Plan pertains to deliverables **D7.3** (and **the third and final update D7.4**) in Task 7.1 within the WP 7 Information, Communication, Upscaling, and Capacity-Building of the Europe-LAND project under Grant Agreement No. 101081307.

It is intended to provide a detailed strategy for CDUE activities for the whole project duration to enable the project to reach its intended reach and impact. As a living document with yearly updates, it **is** continuously adapted and improved to accommodate changing communication needs and opportunities. Besides the intended communication activities, the document also details a monitoring and evaluation framework set-up for CDUE activities and to measure and quantify project impact.

This **second update** of the CDUE-Plan is due to be delivered in August 2025 (M27) and will be updated **one more** time in the course of the project in month 39 (D7.4). **All changes made to the text within the frame of the first update are marked in green, all amendments or changes in this second update are marked in red.**

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1. Introduction

Within the Europe-LAND project, work package 7 aims to generate visibility and awareness of the project and its activities as well as to engage and empower project stakeholders to build upon the outcomes on the longer term. WP7 will undertake a set of information, communication, upscaling and outreach activities, as well as capacity building programmes dedicated to land-use and land management in Europe to achieve these goals. In order to ensure maximum effectiveness and reach of the proposed activities, a detailed plan is needed. This deliverable D7.1 CDUE-Plan and its subsequent yearly updates explain in detail the strategy behind the communication, dissemination, upscaling and exploitation activities of the project.

As described in D1.1, section 3.3, the project differentiates between the terms “communication”, “dissemination”, and “exploitation”. For working definitions of the terms, please refer to D1.1. Communication focuses on informing about the project, whilst dissemination focuses on sharing project results. Exploitation aims at making use of project results through upscaling and replication of outcomes across Europe and beyond. All three forms of activities are relevant to the Europe-LAND project.

This deliverable explains in detail internal and external communications of the project. The most relevant stakeholders for the project were identified as well as their preferred communication channels. Based on this, a variety of communication activities will be utilized to reach the relevant stakeholders. These activities as well as the chosen approach are laid out in this document. A strategy for online communication via a project website and social media is also explained. As exploitation and upscaling of project results is of special interest to the Europe-LAND project, one section of this deliverable details how the proposed activities will aid the implementation of project results by stakeholders. As all partners of the project consortium will be actively involved in communication and dissemination activities, the document also outlines responsibilities of partners when communicating externally. Lastly, the document lays out a plan for the continuous monitoring and evaluation of communication and dissemination activities to ensure the effectiveness of the strategy.

2. Internal Communication

Internal communication within the Europe-LAND project will happen at two levels:

- a) Communication between the EU and Europe-LAND
- b) Communication amongst project partners

Communication between the EU and Europe-LAND will include regular reports, deliverables etc. via the EU portal, as well as regular email and **usually bi-annual informal exchange scheduled** with the assigned EU project officer from EC-CINEA (**unless overlapping with EU review**). The consortium will inform EC-CINEA before any communication activities which may be expected to generate a major digital impact so that the EU may further support outreach via own channels, and invitations to targeted events and project meetings will be send in advance.

Internal communication amongst the project partners is based on regular teleconferences, emails, the project internal exchange platform, a shared online repository, scheduled face-to-face project assemblies, other meetings and workshops. Communication within the project needs to be fluid and comprehensive in order to assure efficient and high-quality collaborative work. A meeting structure outlining the main scheduled meetings, dates and topics is included in D1.1 Project Handbook and the

periodic updates D1.2, D1.3 and D1.4. Internal project communications will preferably be carried out via the following four channels:

1. **Trello:** As of May 2024, Trello changed its billing policy, rendering the previously established Europe-LAND boards unusable with the amount of project partners working on it simultaneously. As this was not foreseeable during the project application, there was no budget available to obtain a license, and thus Trello had to be abandoned as the main project management tool. Instead, HAW as coordinator and WP7 lead established a dedicated Europe-LAND group on **Microsoft Teams**, with dedicated channels for each work package. This ensures continued communication and collaboration between project partners on various tasks and offers a forum for discussion and planning.
2. **HiDrive:** This is the common project document repository for the whole project. HiDrive allows for real time collaboration on documents, which reduces the need for versioning and makes sharing documents easier. Internally, the folders are structured by work packages and tasks, allowing for a better overview and quick access. For more information on data management and protection, please refer to D1.5 Data Management Plan (M6).
3. **Zoom:** This web-based conferencing tool allows to join web meetings remotely without the need for installing an app, making meetings and conferences faster and easier to hold. Zoom also offers a variety of additional tools, such as build-in polling tools, break-out rooms, collaboration tools and subtitles in multiple languages. Other conferencing tools may also be used, e.g. in case partners organize WP meeting as e-meetings and their institution provides only a different tool.
4. **Regular E-mail/Europe-LAND Mailing list:** An internal list of emails of all partners working on the project has been collected and sorted into 4 categories: lead PI, team member, finance, legal and administration. This division allows targeted outreach when dealing with different issues within the project. This communication list is used to announce urgent matters and to carry out communications and management activities. The list is continuously updated and maintained by the WP1 and WP7 leaders.

3. External Communication and Dissemination of Results

3.1 Objectives

Unsustainable land-use is one of the major drivers behind climate change and plays a key role in several other sustainability issues such as food security, biodiversity and the provision of renewable resources. As such, it is of crucial importance to effectively communicate the potential of sustainable land-use and land management for climate change mitigation and adaptation to a variety of stakeholders in order to drive the change towards a more sustainable system.

The Europe-LAND project is committed to not only openly and freely share all project results and the methodology applied but further to emphasize their value to the general public, policy makers and land-use stakeholders. A strategic planning of all external communication is necessary to maximize its effect and lead to the envisaged impact.

The specific objectives behind external communication within the project can be summarized in the following clusters:

1. **Visibility:** Making the project, its activities and results visible and known by a wide range of stakeholders and target audiences
2. **Networking:** Exchanging information and resources with expert stakeholders and other projects to build connections and form synergies for mutual input
3. **Exploitation and Upscaling:** Preparing project information, methodology and results to be implemented in new contexts and applied to scenarios outside the scope of the project.

3.2 Audiences

Based on the focus and the objectives of the Europe-LAND project, four main groups of target audiences were identified and a detailed analysis of their preferred communication channels was carried out in course of the first version of the CDUE-Plan (D7.1). The main target audiences and the results of the analysis are compiled in Table 1.

Table 1: Target Audience Groups and preferred communication channels

Target Audience Group	Target audience sub-groups	Preferred communication channels
Land-use stakeholders	e.g. land-users, land-owners, farmers, agriculture organizations, foresters, forestry organizations, landscape and national park authorities	Agricultural Fairs and exhibitions, podcast programs, Social media platforms such as Facebook and Twitter (X), website, workshops and webinars, local newspapers, email newsletters
Public authorities	e.g. local, regional and national authorities, regulatory agencies, policy makers, farm federations, citizen associations	Policy briefs and reports, workshops and webinars, stakeholder meetings, media outreach, Social media platforms such as LinkedIn and Twitter (X)
Scientific community	e.g. experts, researchers, NGOs, spatial planning engineers, science communicators	Academic publications, webinars, social media, email newsletters, scientific conferences and events, social media platforms such as LinkedIn and Twitter (X)
Extended target group	General public, consumers, media	Social media platforms such as Twitter (X) and LinkedIn, traditional media via press releases , newspapers, podcasts,

Since this initial identification of main stakeholder groups, the project consortium compiled an extensive list of relevant stakeholder data for local, regional and national stakeholders from each

category from all partner countries, as a basis for the stakeholder work in WP3, which was then adapted into the stakeholder pool as part of the D7.6 Stakeholder Engagement Strategy. Extensive information on the formation, maintenance and usage of the Stakeholder Pool can be found in D6.7 Stakeholder Engagement Strategy supplementary report and on the stakeholder engagement website (<https://europe-land.eu/join-us/>).

The stakeholder pool is continuously updated and expanded, by encouraging potential stakeholders through all outreach and dissemination activities to sign up through the dedicated form on the project website.

For data protection purposes, the personal data of stakeholders who have given consent to be included in the stakeholder pool is restricted to use by the WP7 team only. It is made available to project partners only after signing a confidentiality agreement, to be used solely within the project's scope. A version of the stakeholder pool with redacted personal data is available to the project consortium on the project **HiDrive at WP7/T7.3 Strategic Stakeholder Engagement/Stakeholder Pool**.

The stakeholder pool is utilized to identify relevant participants for project activities, recipients of project information and invitations to events and to more effectively disseminate project outcomes to the relevant groups and to stakeholders who have expressed interest in specific topics. It is also used to identify relevant experts, authorities and contacts for certain inputs to project work (e.g. expert interviews, roundtables, policy sessions, etc.).

3.3 Approach

Based on the identified communication channels used by the target audiences of the Europe-LAND project and the Grant Agreement, the project will employ a range of external communication tools and channels listed below in chapter 3.3.1 and 3.3.2 to maximize the reach and impact of the project. The following section lists the planned communication activities and online communication. This list will be updated and adjusted according to changing needs over the project duration, which will be reflected in the yearly updates of this CDUE-Plan (D7.2, D7.3, D7.4) in the scope of Task 7.1.

In order to ensure that all external communication of the project is coherent and recognizable, a project brand consisting of a logo, poster, flyer and templates for public presentations as well as deliverables was created and shared with the consortium partners to be used for dissemination activities. The project brand can be found on the shared project HiDrive: **WP7-> T7.2 Project branding, communication material and digital outreach**.

3.3.1 Main Activities

In an effort to achieve the communication objectives of the Europe-LAND project, a wide range of dissemination and communication activities are planned over the course of the project. They are laid out in more detail in the following section and comprise promotional material, a project video, regular project newsletters, oral and virtual presentations, technical workshops and capacity-building seminars, webinars, open access publications, podcasts and press releases. **Any activities to promote the project already scheduled within the next 12 months can be found in table 2. This list will be complemented and extended as new opportunities arise.** The activities planned in this section are subject to the continuous reporting within T7.4 and will be included in D7.7 and D7.8.

Table 2: Pre-planned communication and dissemination activities over the next 12 months (M27 to M39)

August 2025 (M27)		
26-29.08.2025	XVIII EAAE Congress Food System Transformation in Challenging Times in Bonn, Germany	IAMO
September 2025 (M28)		
TBC	Release of 2 nd Podcast series	HAW, UCPH
09-11.09.25	IACS Community Exchange (ICE) Conference 2025	IAMO
02-05.09.25	IALE 2025 European Landscape Ecology Congress	SUA
October 2025 (M29)		
TBC	IACS Data Community of Practice bi-annual meeting, online	HAW
02-04.10.25	Agroecology Europe Forum 2025, Malmo, Sweden	UC
15-17.10.25	International Forum on Agroecosystem Living Labs (IFALL) 2025	IGAR
29.10.2025	Health soil as the base for change, Nitra, Slovakia	SUA
December 2025 (M31)		
TBC	Release of the third project newsletter	HAW, all partners
February 2026 (M33)		
TBC	FIRE Workshop (name tbc)	TBC
April 2026 (M35)		
TBC	3 rd Science EU Policy Dialogue, online	HAW
May 2026 (M36)		
TBC	19 th International Scientific Days, High Tatras, Slovakia	SUA
June 2026 (M37)		
12.06.26	IACS Data Community of Practice Bi-annual meeting, Vienna	HAW
August 2026 (M39)		
10-17.08.26	Europe-LAND Summer School in Tartu	EMU
17-21.08.26	IRC 2026 Regional Conference, Istanbul	IGAR, CU, LU, SUA

Project poster and leaflet

As part of the recognizable project brand, a project poster and leaflet were developed and shared with partners for open use in their facilities and at events, workshops and conferences. The standard language of the dissemination material is English. For the project leaflet, a template was created, for partners to customize with their own contact information and for translation into local languages, if needed.

Figure 1: Europe-LAND Project Poster

Project video

A video detailing the project’s scope and objectives was developed by M13. It is displayed on the project website. *Each year of the project, the WP7 team plans to release another video, detailing preliminary results and a final wrap-up of the project achievements in Q1 of 2027.*

Together with WP6, we have released our 2nd Project Video “Developing a digital toolbox for sustainable land-use and land management” on 17 July 2025. The video is available on the project website. Furthermore, we have created a dedicated [YouTube channel](#), for more sufficient dissemination and metric tracking purposes. It will also be utilized as video lecture repository in the frame of the MOOC.

Table 3 shows the list of project videos, and it will be updated within the next update of the CDUE Plan. The third and fourth videos are planned to be produced to disseminate further key e outputs of the project.

Table 3: Project Videos

Number	Title	Link
#1	“Introducing Europe-LAND”	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=KO4Pt-w1fvQ
#2	“Developing a digital toolbox for sustainable land-use and land management”	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=bQkyUfj0Suo

In addition, a spontaneous opportunity to communicate as well as disseminate project outputs could be seized: A video contribution to the EU-wide campaign “#PeatlandsMatter” to be launched in late 2025 by the European Landowners' Organization (ELO), to increase the knowledge of the public, landowners and policymakers regarding European Peatlands. ELO partners in the EUKI Project focusing on [Building the European Peatlands Initiative: A Strong Alliance for Peatland Climate Protection in Europe](#) where they bring together governments, scientists, landowners, and environmental

organizations to strengthen peatland conservation efforts in partnership with [Eurosité – the European Land Conservation Network](#), [CEEweb for Biodiversity](#), and the [Michael Succow Foundation](#) with [the Greifswald Mire Centre](#). In the campaign, Europe-LAND’S wetland expert Prof Piotr Banaszuk from the Bialystok University of Technology is featured in the campaign.

Regular Newsletters

5 periodic newsletters will be published every 6 months starting in M18. It will be made available for download on the project website and will be distributed and advertised over the project’s social media accounts. Topics will be decided by WP7 leaders and articles and contributions created in collaboration with the project partners and potential external experts and stakeholders. We have delivered 2 newsletters (December 2024 and June 2025). The third one is expected to be delivered in December 2025.

Presentations at conferences and events

Consortium partners over the course of the project duration will attend a variety of events and conferences at which they will represent the project, present project results and advertise project outcomes. To ensure a coherent public presence of the project, templates for presentations and dissemination materials such as posters and flyers are provided within the project brand to be used at these public appearances.

In close cooperation with other Horizon Europe land use related projects, we are planning to contribute to an event in Brussels aimed at explicitly reaching out to policy makers and members from EU parliament. This initiative seeks to effectively communicate key project messages to create impact on political and decision-making levels.

Furthermore, presentations and attendances at events and conferences as part of the project dissemination are subject to the continuous reporting to the project coordinator and the EU. An internal reporting system is set-up to allow for easy reporting of such activities, which will feed into the deliverables D7.7 and D7.8 in T7.4 and will periodically be updated in the EU portal.

Figure 2: Impressions from some presentations at external events

Technical workshops and seminars

One key element to exploit project results are technical workshops and seminars that will be organized by WP7 leaders in collaboration with various consortium partners to reach a wide range of audiences. As sketched in the Grant Agreement (page 22, table 2.2.2b), the list of already planned technical

workshops may be extended over the course of the project, when further subjects of interest or relevant target audiences are identified by project partners.

Table 4: Technical workshops already planned.

Short description	Who	Target audience
Revealing land-use behaviour and its drivers in Europe	HAW & UCPH	Researchers and land users, which can be localfarmers, agrobusinesses or public authorities. The workshop “Leveraging data from the Integrated Administration and Control System (IACS) for research” was held on 19-21 February 2025, in Hamburg, Germany.
Towards a better understanding of land-use decisions related to climate change and biodiversity	HAW & IGAR	Land users, managers, local authorities, regulatory agencies. “Land use and land management strategies for climate change and biodiversity conservation” was organised on August 29, 2024, 8:30-11:30, within the 35th International Geographical Congress, 2024, Dublin, Ireland, 24-30 August 2024.
Prospective trends in the mapping of future expected land use and land cover patterns	HAW & UL	Local authorities, regulatory agencies, decision-makers. The technical workshop “Prospective trends in the mapping of future expected land use and land cover patterns” was held on 24 April 2025, online.
New economic and behavioural tools insupport of mitigation and adaptation	HAW & SUA	Land users, decision-makers, regulatory agencies.
Introducing the Europe-LAND toolbox	HAW & AUTH	Policy makers, local authorities, regulatory agencies, farm federations and agriculture organizations, spatial planning engineers, NGOs, citizen associations, researchers and anyone interested in the topic.

Resembling slight adjustment of the sketched schedule indicated in the Grant Agreement, the first technical workshop in collaboration with WP2 on revealing land-use behaviour and its drivers in Europe was moved from originally envisaged M12 to M21 to meet with experts once the harmonized database of land use and land management for Europe (D2.1, due M18) is readily available as a base for discussion. The other technical workshops may equally be adjusted slightly to better reflect the project’s timeline and to discuss key deliverables and outputs with relevant stakeholders and experts.

Webinars

Within the D7.6 Stakeholder Engagement Strategy, a series of 6 expert webinars were scheduled within the first year of the project as one of the key participatory actions. WP7 in collaboration with the other WP leaders managed to organize a total of 7 expert webinars in the first 12 months of the project, reaching 425 registered participants. Beyond the finalization of the expert webinar series, the consortium agreed to organize less frequent expert webinars, however, then directly focusing on promoting and exploiting concrete recent deliverables, to further engage with stakeholders and disseminate project outputs in a proven format over the project duration. **For example, we are planning to organize a webinar regarding Wetland in mid-September.**

Science EU Policy Dialogue

Jointly with our sister projects **PLUS Change** and **MOSAIC**, we have annually implemented EU Science-Policy Dialogues to address sustainable land use and management. By uniting policymakers, scientists, and civil society, these dialogues aim to:

- improve the joint understanding of the different perspectives and needs of policy and science, also paying attention to civil society perspectives, on European land use, land management and closely related fields.
- explore existing needs, constraints and opportunities and to identify appropriate solutions to effectively address existing challenges both on research and policy-making levels; and
- propose suitable approaches and concrete settings for the design and co-creation of sustainable land use strategies in close collaboration with policymakers.

The first Science- EU Policy dialogue took place on 16 April 2024, and the second Science- EU Policy dialogue took place in April 2025. We plan to continue this dialogue as shown below:

- The third Science- EU Policy dialogue will take place in April 2026.
- The final Science- EU Policy dialogue will take place in April 2027 or in the frame of the final conference at the latest in May 2027 (envisaged as joint event organized by the three sister projects in Brussels).

Figure 3: Science EU Policy Dialogue

Open Access Scientific Publications and Reports

Europe-LAND project results will be arranged to develop peer-reviewed articles, book chapters and reports intended for scientific audiences. These scientific outputs will cover theoretical issues, conceptual and methodological questions and key results. In addition, research data will be made available as much as possible. All scientific publications will be open access whenever possible. Publications, including public deliverables, are immediately uploaded to the dedicated Europe-LAND community on Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/communities/europeland/>) and the project website (<https://europe-land.eu/results/>) to maximize the reach.

Podcasts

A public dedicated podcast series titled “European Land Use Talks” was conceptualized, focusing on key project results and supplementary research findings, as well as practical examples, dialogues with

experts and stakeholders and discussions. The episodes will be 5 to 10 minutes long each, with a dedicated topic and invited guests. The first episode will be released by M17.

The episodes will be recorded and produced by WP7 leaders. The launch was pushed back to be able to reflect on first outputs of the project. The podcast series will allow to attract an audience that prefers to listening to project results rather than reading newsletters or reports.

The first podcast episode, introducing the overall context of the project, was released on 7 March 2025. The episode is available on [Podigee](#) and [Spotify](#). The second episode is planned to be released by the end of summer 2025.

Figure 4: Europe-LAND Podcast

Press releases

In order to enhance visibility of the Europe-LAND project and to inform all target audiences about the project, traditional media will be supplied with one press release per year. The main media companies in the partner countries relevant to the project are listed in table 5. Besides, PR offices of partner organizations might further support dissemination of press releases over their networks. The first press release of the project was produced by HAW Hamburg in English and German and released in M13. Several translations and publications in local languages were done by project partners. A detailed list of all press releases and media articles featuring the Europe-LAND project will be included in D7.7 first report on dissemination (due in M24). A second press release has been sent off in M27, disseminating the WP4 modelling deliverable, and further will follow as to disseminate upcoming results to expert and lay media alike.

Table 5: Media companies in the partner countries relevant to the project

Country	Media companies
Austria	Krone Zeitung Der Standard Presse Kleine Zeitung ORF
Czech Republic	Dnes Deník Hospořáské noviny
Denmark	Politiken Weekendavisen Altinget.dk

	Jyllands Posten Berlingske Tidende
Estonia	Daily: Postimees; Eesti Päevaleht; Ohtuleht Weekly: Eest Ekspress; Maaleht
Germany	Die Zeit FAZ Der Spiegel Süddeutsche Zeitung TAZ
Greece	Efimerida ron Syntakton To Vima Kathimerini
Italy	Corriere della Sera La Repubblica
Latvia	Latvijas Avīze Neatkarīgā Rīta Avīze
Portugal	Público Expresso Jornal de Notícias Observador
Poland	Gazeta Wyborcza Fakt Rzeczypospolita Portal Onet
Romania	Adevărul Libertatea
Slovakia	Pravda Hospodárske noviny Roľnícke noviny

In addition to the CDUE-Plan (D7.1, this first update D7.2 and following updates D7.3, D7.4) a dedicated Stakeholder Engagement Strategy (D7.6) was developed and submitted in M6, detailing a planning for all participatory actions involving stakeholders within the project. The following points are included in D7.6 in greater detail: a) an expert webinar series, b) regular expert exchanges, c) a yearly Science-EU Policy Dialogue, d) continuous collaboration with relevant research projects, and e) a final conference reaching at least 100 stakeholders at the end of the project.

3.3.2 Online Communication

In addition to the planned activities to disseminate and communicate project outputs, a broad online presence was established for the Europe-LAND project. Online communication plays a key role in reaching all stakeholder groups as well as the general public to maximize the reach and impact of the project. The means established for online communication are the dedicated project website and an account on LinkedIn, pertaining to Milestone 4 (reached in M6). Planned activities for the website and social media accounts are laid out in the following section.

Website

Serving as a home base for all communications, the website (www.europe-land.eu) is a key channel to communicate project activities to all target audience groups. The main language of the website is English, but sections in local languages of the partners will be added where appropriate to engage more potential stakeholders.

The project website consists of seven sections detailing different aspects of the project.

Section one is the ‘Home’ landing page, displaying an introduction to the project, the first project video and the three most recent news posts and events. The second section, the ‘About’ tab details the project outline, the project’s vision and methodology, the scope of project activities and a map as well as detailed descriptions of the eight case studies. The ‘Partners’ tab lists all 13 project partners and two associates with their logo and a link to their official website. The fourth is the ‘News’ section, where articles about project activities, event recaps, and related topics are published. An internal list for the planning and tracking of the publications in this section is set up in HiDrive within WP7. A separate ‘Events’ section is utilised to announce upcoming events organized by the project. Past events are archived on the website and whenever possible, event material such as agendas and presentations, are made available for download. One of the central sections of the website is the ‘Results’ tab, on which all public deliverables, scientific publications, and newsletters are made available for download. Some of the deliverables, such as the toolbox developed within WP6, will be hosted on partner’s local websites to facilitate the set up. The ‘Results’ section of the project website will include links to any external resources. The deliverable D7.6 Stakeholder Engagement Strategy was delivered in form of a dedicated section on the project website, the seventh section titled ‘Join Us’. This section contains a detailed description of the Stakeholder Engagement Strategy, all planned participatory actions and easy-to-use forms to sign up to the stakeholder pool and the network of EU projects. More information on the Stakeholder Engagement Strategy can be found in the D7.6 supplementary report.

The website will be maintained for at least 5 years after the project duration ends, to ensure maximum exploitation.

Project partner websites

In order to maximize the reach of the project communication, each partner may use their organization’s website to share important outputs of the project. Table 6 compiles all partner websites.

Table 6: Project partner websites

Partner	website URL
HAW	https://www.haw-hamburg.de/en/ftz-nk/
AUTH	https://www.auth.gr/en/
EMU	https://pk.emu.ee/en/structure/environmentalprotectionandlandscapemanagement/
UCPH	https://ign.ku.dk/english/research/geography/land_use_earth-observation-and-sustainability/
UC	Centre for Functional Ecology: https://cfe.uc.pt/ Department of Life Sciences: https://www.uc.pt/fctuc/dcv/ University of Coimbra: https://www.uc.pt/
UNIBO	https://scienzeaziendali.unibo.it/en/index.html

IGAR	http://geoinst.ro/index.html
BUT	Main page: https://pb.edu.pl/en/ Faculty of Engineering Management: https://wiz.pb.edu.pl/en/ Faculty of Civil Engineering and Environmental Sciences: https://wb.pb.edu.pl/en/
LU	https://www.lu.lv/en/
SUA	Main page: https://www.uniag.sk/en/main-page Faculty of Economics and Management: https://fem.uniag.sk/en/home/
BOKU	https://boku.ac.at/en/wiso/sec
IAMO	https://lsg.iamo.de/
CU	https://www.natur.cuni.cz/eng https://www.tilspec.cz/

Social Media

To maximize the public reach and awareness of project results, the project will be extensively promoted on social media channels. Based on the target audience analysis presented in section 3.2, most target groups can be reached by establishing presence on LinkedIn. Multimedia content like pictures, infographics and videos generated from project reports, events and partner activities are posted to relevant groups and pages, to invite public exchange about the project and its implications for land-use practices, policy and research. All facts and figures will be referenced to the corresponding website page to lead interested parties to the relevant contact persons.

All posts are planned and scheduled in advance to ensure regular activity on the channels. A detailed social media planning containing information on each post, a responsible person, a scheduled posting time and actual posting time is available on HiDrive: **WP7 -> T7.2 Europe-LAND project branding, communication material and digital outreach -> Social Media.**

LinkedIn is being employed to establish a mass online networking community, the Community of Practice (CoP) to build synergies. A detailed plan was developed in scope of D7.5 Action-Plan for Community of Practice delivered in M9. It contains details on how the consortium aims to build, maintain and manage the CoP.

To maximize the reach on social media and make sure to reach intended audiences and interested parties, appropriate hashtags will be used for each post. As a base for all posts the hashtags #Landuse; #Sustainability; #Agriculture and #CINEA were identified. For specific posts regarding webinars or findings, workshops, policy relevant information etc. the posts will indicate these activities and topics with corresponding hashtags (e.g. #Workshop; #Webinar; #Policy).

LinkedIn

A LinkedIn company page was set up for the Europe-LAND project. It is available here: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/europe-land/>. The page is managed by HAW as WP7 lead with the aim to share weekly updates on the project activities and results, events as well as relevant information on land-use in Europe in general as well as facilitate the CoP. LinkedIn is an ideal platform to connect with experts and professional stakeholders and foster a network for potential synergies. At the time of

submission of this deliverable, the LinkedIn page of Europe-LAND had 519 followers (as of 11 August 2025)

Figure 5: The Europe-LAND LinkedIn page

X

In the past, X has been an effective tool to reach policymakers, the scientific community as well as the general public. Starting in 2023, X has undergone several unfavourable developments, which have led many official and scientific members to leave the platform. As such, the decision to establish a project account on X was postponed to M15 in frame of this first update of the CDUE-Plan. After careful consideration of X and alternatives (for example Mastodon), the WP7 lead has made the decision to go ahead with the original plan to establish a project account on X. Despite the changes to the platform, X remains one of the major communication platforms for many policy officials, academia and business. The dedicated project account was created in M15 and can be found here: https://x.com/EuropeLAND_EU.

Besides the dedicated LinkedIn and X accounts for the project, which will be maintained by HAW and be updated in English, project partners might employ their own institutions' social media accounts on different platforms to post about the most important updates or advertise local events. The local accounts might be useful to reach local stakeholders who are not using the main social media platforms or are communicating in local languages. A list of partners' social media accounts is compiled in table 7.

Table 7: Project partners' social media accounts

Partner	Social Media handle
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HAW	LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/company/research-and-transfer-center-sustainable-development-and-climate-change-management
AUTH	Instagram: https://www.instagram.com/auth_university_thessaloniki/ Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/Aristoteleio/ LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/company/aristotle-university-of-thessaloniki-auth/?originalSubdomain=gr X: https://twitter.com/Aristoteleio
EMU	Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/EMUkeskkonnakaitse
UCPH	LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/school/university-of-copenhagen/
UC	Centre for Functional Ecology Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/CFEUC Instagram: https://www.instagram.com/cfe_uc/ LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/company/centre-for-functional-ecology-science-for-people-the-planet/ X: https://twitter.com/CFE_UC YouTube: https://www.youtube.com/@CentreforFunctionalEcology Department of Life Sciences Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/fctucDCV Instagram: https://www.instagram.com/dcv_uc/ X: https://twitter.com/DCV_UC YouTube: https://www.youtube.com/@departamentodecienciasdavi8940/featured University of Coimbra Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/univdecoimbra Instagram: https://www.instagram.com/ucoimbra/ X: https://twitter.com/univdecoimbra YouTube: https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCwJWYs4uKz77qR_NaruUcBg LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/school/universidade-de-coimbra/
UNIBO	LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/showcase/disa-universit%C3%A0-di-bologna/?originalSubdomain=it YouTube: https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLaUmBQ7P5K-C9D_vHNFLK-Vk8-5eQMxXf
BUT	LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/school/politechnika-bia%C5%82ostocka/?originalSubdomain=pl
LU	LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/company/university-of-latvia/ Instagram: https://www.instagram.com/universitate/ Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/latvijasuniversitate/ X: https://twitter.com/universitately
SUA	Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/SPUNitra/ Instagram: https://www.instagram.com/spunitra/
BOKU	Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/socialecologyvienna/ X: https://twitter.com/BOKU_SEC Instagram: https://www.instagram.com/boku_sec/
IAMO	X: https://twitter.com/iamoLSG https://bsky.app/profile/iamo-lsg.bsky.social

CU	Facebook: https://www.facebook.com/kagik.cuni https://www.facebook.com/prf.uk.praha Instagram: https://www.instagram.com/kagik.cuni/?hl=cs https://www.instagram.com/natur_cuni/?hl=cs
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4. Exploitation and Upscaling

With the measures and activities laid out so far, Europe-LAND will ensure a wide visibility and networking of the project. However, the project also strives to go beyond the communication and dissemination of project activities and outputs to widen the project’s impact: It delivers knowledge, tools and methodologies that can be further developed and reused, i.e. exploited by others. A dedicated Exploitation Strategy for the project results will be developed within Task 6.5 and will be detailed in deliverable D6.5 Exploitation Plan due in M46, drawing out a detailed planning on establishing and exploiting project results beyond the scope and duration of the project. In the frame of this deliverable D7.3 and its subsequent updates, a more general plan for the exploitation and upscaling of project results over the whole course of the project will be drawn out.

The project partners defined some priorities for the exploitation of results in the Grant Agreement:

- “To foster and encourage the deployment of innovative tools;
- to create a virtuous and sustainable loop between research and innovation;
- to ensure the strong commitment of the project stakeholders, from policy-makers to citizens;
- to widely spread the knowledge on the demonstrated tools generated by the project, so that as many organizations as possible may benefit from them.”

To achieve these goals, Europe-LAND will employ various measures. All methodology, as far as possible, will be made freely available and replicability will be a main concern, which all partners will work towards. Furthermore, capacity building programmes such as workshops, webinars, a MOOC and a summer school, as well as the toolbox and various stakeholder collaborations will aid in making project results available and applicable for stakeholders to act as multipliers, and to adapt project results to new contexts and areas. Table 8 lists specific project outputs and by which stakeholder group they might be taken up for further exploitation. An extended version including sensitive project outputs as well as some supplementary project internal information can be found in D1.3 Project Handbook second update table 3. The Europe-LAND Community of Practice (CoP), established online, is fostering networking and discussions on the methodology and outputs and creating direct feedback loops with external experts, relevant EU projects and policymakers. It will serve as a long-lasting platform on current and future land-use and land management issues across Europe, beyond the project duration, sustained by the Coordinator.

Table 8: Specific project outputs and possible target groups for exploitation

WP	Specific output	Uptake by whom?/Examples
2	Harmonized database of IACS data from European countries	Regional, national and EU policy makers in the frame of the technical workshop on 19-21 Feb, including representatives from DG Agri, JRC “Leveraging data from the Integrated Administration and

		Control System (IACS) for research”, in the frame of ongoing IACS Community exchanges
2	Dataset on farm typologies across EU – similarities in crop patterns, efficacy of subsidies	Regional, national and EU policy makers for tailoring future subsidy schemes spatially, in the frame of ongoing IACS Community exchanges
2	Living lab on policy effects on land-use changes across the EU Instead of “Living lab” approach, we have been working as “participatory stakeholder engagement”	Regional, national and EU policy makers in the frame of annual Science EU Policy Dialogues
2	Database and report on greenhouse gas emissions of wetlands	Regional, national and EU policy makers, e.g. Sustainable Development Observatory in European Economic and Social Committee EU representatives of farmers’ union organisations Dissemination of ongoing work in the frame of expert webinars e.g. on “Peatland Perspectives: Latest Data on Distribution, Agricultural Practices and Emission Factors in the EU”, online campaign #PeatlandMatters
3	Report on assessment of policy incentives and instruments related to land-use decisions	Policy makers and governments on EU, national, regional and local levels, e.g. in the frame of the 2025 Science EU Policy Dialogues
3	Report on land-use decision making – local drivers of land-use decisions	Decision-making stakeholders: national, regional and local authorities, interest groups and experts, e.g. in the frame of the WP3 Mirror Workshops, expert interviews in each case study country (total interviewed experts: 40)
3	Online workshops for raising awareness and best-practice examples	Decision-making stakeholders: ministries, regulatory agencies, experts, also in the frame of upcoming outreach action targeting EU decision makers. The first workshop took place online on 16 th May 2025, entitled “Sustainable Land Use and Land Management: Emerging Trends, Current Challenges, and European Solutions”, attended by 70 participants.
4	Report on harmonized location factors affecting land-use and land cover transition	Development planning authorities, e.g. in the frame of conference presentations
4	Mapping of future expected land-use patterns	National, regional and local level planning authorities, specifically in sectors like nature conservation, forestry, agriculture

		e.g. by means of wide dissemination of Europe-LAND Cards and Success Stories for application of modelling tools
4	Development of standardised land-use/land cover transition indicators	National and regional level authorities working on development planning, e.g. in the frame of conference presentations
5	Analysis of telecoupling frameworks on land-use, climate change and biodiversity protection	EU, national, regional and local level policy -makers; academia, e.g. in the frame of conference presentations and scientific publications
5	Europe-LAND telecoupling framework including evaluation of various socio-spatial structures	EU-level decision-makers; national, regional and local level policy -makers; spatial planners; academia, e.g. in the frame of conference presentations and scientific publications
5	Model of future land-use change for 2050	EU, national, regional and local level policy -makers; spatial planners; academia, e.g. in the frame of conference presentations and scientific publications
6	Developed and tested Toolbox	Land users, land managers, policy makers e.g. through webinars like “Towards an interactive digital Toolbox on sustainable land-use” and further events
6	Serious gaming approach for scenario exploration	Land managers, decision making stakeholders on regional level, e.g. in the frame of conference presentations
6	Open access MOOC and Summer School	Young professionals; MOOC to be released end of 2025/beginning of 2026
6	Technical capacity building seminars	All stakeholder groups

Some of the expected outcomes of Europe-LAND might also directly contribute to certain policy objectives. A list detailing such outcomes, expected delivery dates and relevant policy areas is added in table 9. The listed expected results were announced by Europe-LAND partners during the first installation of the Science-EU Policy Dialogue, organized on 16th April 2024 and will be further elaborated during the following yearly installments of this participatory action, ensuring that EU officers joining the event will be made aware of the upcoming policy-relevant outputs.

Table 9: Expected project results with policy relevance

WP	Expected research result	Which policy area will be targeted?	When will they be delivered?
2	Farm typologies across EU	Agriculture / land use	May 2025
6	Adaptation of Scenario Exploration System (SES) for participatory exploration of land use pathways (on a local/regional level)	land use (drivers, incentives, conflicts)	Mid 2025

5	Telecoupling framework for assessing and modelling land- use strategies	CAP, biodiversity protection, climate change adaptation, sustainable development	First internal draft November 2024/full version November 2025
3	For regional case studies across EU: Identify drivers of land- use decision-making and then model LULCC trajectories until 2050 with a focus on land- use decision making	land- use drivers, subsidy schemes, incentives	Late 2024/2025 first results, final 2027
2	EU- wide quantification of land- related GHG flux trajectories from drained and cultivated European wetlands	climate change, mitigation, land use	End of 2026
2	Drivers of LULCC for 2050	EU land use, land use drivers	Early 2027
6	Toolbox: interactive display of collected data and future predictions on land use and land cover changes for Europe	Climate change, land use (agriculture, forestry), disaster risk management	Early 2027

IACS Data Community of Practice

IACS Data Community of Practice was established to facilitate cooperation and exchanges of related research, between researchers, policy makers and practitioners working with IACS data. This CoP emerged from the technical workshop “Leveraging data from the Integrated Administration and Control System (IACS) for research” which took place in Hamburg, Germany, 19-21 February 2025, and since then we have been actively in communication, including the dissemination of the relevant events, publications. To date, the active Community has identified 10 work areas;

1. Develop user guides and publications addressing challenges and solutions
2. Produce policy briefs and expert opinions
3. Compile a list of interventions (in IACS or AEMS)
4. Compare ‘optimal’ vs. real-world implementation of measures
5. Utilize EU-wide IACS data for insights on crop diversity and rotation
6. Explore new proposals (e.g., on nitrogen use and land-use intensity)
7. Establish a strong network of IACS data experts
8. Expand and enhance the IACS database

9. Integrate and enrich datasets through harmonization

10. Identify and respond to relevant funding opportunities

For example, as a part of task 1, a set of CoP members, among them external experts and Europe-LAND partners, are coordinating a special issue *“Leveraging agricultural data from the EU’s Integrated Administration and Control System (IACS) for research and policy”* on *Journal of Land Use Science*, to be published in 2026.

Current number of members: 31 (As of 11 August 2025)

5. Partner responsibilities

HAW Hamburg is the lead of WP7 and therefore the main responsibility of managing, monitoring and reporting regarding communication and dissemination as well as upscaling and exploitation lies with the HAW. Nevertheless, all partners play a crucial role in achieving dissemination goals and are therefore involved in the activities of WP7. Partners have received funding for various activities such as open access publications and attendance to conferences, hosting project events and preparing dissemination materials. Some partners also hold special responsibility for co-hosting webinars, events, the MOOC and summer school. In addition, all partners might be asked by WP7 leads to contribute information, pictures or short texts on their respective expertise and work within the project for use on social media or the website or to contribute to one of the newsletters. During the project preparation, all partners were asked to allocate some staff efforts to WP7 for this purpose.

In order to ensure a coherent and recognizable project brand, all partners are strongly encouraged to use the provided templates for dissemination activities, which can be found in the project brand package on HiDrive: **WP7-> T7.2 Project branding, communication material and digital outreach.**

During all dissemination activities, partners are responsible for accurately acknowledging EU-funding according to the agreed-upon terms in the Grant Agreement, in order to be eligible for funding of said communication activities.

All partners are furthermore responsible for reporting all dissemination and communication activities to WP7 leads within one week, or for open access publications immediately, to be included in the continuous project reporting internally as well as towards the EU.

6. Monitoring and evaluation of CDUE activities

In order to ensure a high-quality execution of the communication strategy, continuous monitoring and evaluation is of high importance. The Europe-LAND project **therefore established an overall monitoring and evaluation framework in scope of T1.4 and D1.8 in M6**. However, a separate monitoring focused on CDUE activities is vital to ensure that the project will achieve the intended impact.

In course of the project, WP7 will produce deliverables comprising reports and records of the wide range of planned dissemination and communication activities. D7.7 (M24) and D7.8 (M48) will comprise extensive reports on all dissemination activities and online communication laid out in this CDUE-Plan and its yearly updates that will have taken place during the respective reporting periods (M1 to M24 and M25 to M48). This information will also be continuously updated on the EU portal by

the WP7 leader. Additionally, D6.6 (M45) will give a summary of the technical capacity building seminars carried out over the course of the project.

Besides tracking the dissemination and communication activities themselves with the internally set-up trackings for events attended, publications, social media and website posts and following the schedule for webinars, workshops, events, podcasts, etc. and the deliverables mentioned above, the project also aims to measure how effective these communication actions are and to quantify the impact of them.

In order to do so, some key performance indicators (KPIs) were defined in the Grant Agreement and will be monitored over the course of the project. The KPIs defined are listed in [table 10](#) (see next page). [For this first update, the results achieved can be found in the column "M15", and for the second update in the column "M27".](#)

Table 10: Key performance indicators for the impact of communication and dissemination activities

Key performance indicators	Poor impact	Good impact	Excellent impact	M15	M27
Material downloads from website	<100	100-200	>200	104	8640 (website 570; 8070 Zenodo, as of 16.08.25)
Relevant contacts made through website	<15	15-30	>30	14	34
Number of followers on social media	<500	500-1000	>1000	331	532
Number of interactions (e.g. likes, comments, shares)	<800	800-1200	>1200	640 likes, 8 comments, 16 shares	1384 likes, 20 comments, 42 shares (as of 11.08.25)
Number of papers submitted	<10	10-15	>15	1	9
Number of publications downloaded on website	<30	30-50	>50	0	40 (as of 16.08.25)
Number of brochures distributed	<300	300-500	>500	100	100
Number of video views	<500	500-1000	>1000	-	60 (Since setting up our YouTube channel – 17.07.25)
Number of newsletter subscribers	<500	500-1000	>1000	-	775
Number of cooperations with projects and initiatives	<5	5-15	>15	2	9
Number of events organized	<6	6-10	>10	2	27
Number of external events attended	<6	6-10	>10	9	44
Number of total people reached through events by the end of the project	<100	100-500	>500	340	2877
Members in communities of practice	<1000	1000-1500	>1500	331	563
Number of followers of podcast series	<500	500-1000	>1000	-	16
Number of webinars held	<3	3-5	>5	7	9
Number of participants/webinar	<50	50-150	>150	425 total	425 total
Number of workshops held	<3	3-5	>5	1	17
Number of participants/workshop	<10	10-30	>30	22	830
Number of participants of final conference	<50	50-100	>100	-	-